

ROLE MODELS, EDI AND LIGHTHOUSES

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I have a long-standing interest in the importance of gender and diversity in the workplace, universities specifically. I work toward changes in policy and visibility: in the past I've worked on governance with the University Council (some 15 years ago), and when people ask me to provide suggestions for keynotes, I deliberately send lists with only women. Recently, though, for all kinds of reasons I've been paying more attention to other kinds of diversity.

Veterinary medicine is notoriously non-diverse; in the USA numbers as high as 94% white, non-hispanic veterinarians in the workforce have been reported (1). I don't know the numbers in Europe (am happy to hear from those who have numbers), but from looking around me I expect about the same. This is obviously problematic for all kinds of reasons, including mental well-being of veterinarians (2) and development of cultural humility (3), which are both essential to future work in the veterinary field.

This lack of diversity so obviously needs to change, but it is overwhelming to think about where to start. How to work toward inclusivity, and get a critical mass of diverse students to make it easier for everyone to feel welcome, at home, seen? At this week's Netherlands Society for Medical Education conference in Egmond aan Zee, the session I attended on role models was both hopeful and frustrating.

Hopeful: research by Isabella Spaans indicating that (human) medical students don't really identify a single role model, but compose a "mosaic" role model (4), forming an "ideal" role model meshed from characteristics from various people, and that this is very similar in students from migration backgrounds compared to non-migration backgrounds. To me this means that *all* of us can be role models, and we don't need to be perfect role models on all aspects to be of value as a role model.

Frustrating: In a follow-up to Isabella Spaans' study, she showed students from migration backgrounds indicated much less of a feeling that they resemble their role models than students from non-migration backgrounds. And this is hardly surprising; it is easier for anyone to identify with a person that shares common experiences, and without role models that share such fundamental experiences as growing up with a migration background, its not hard to see how identification with a role model is missing.

I've no answers here, except that we need to do better. But I'm also not sure how to have diverse role models as a lighthouse to other students and future veterinarians, while not asking too much from the role models themselves- being a lighthouse in the middle of town can be a lonely place.

How do we work toward more diversity in Veterinary Medicine? I'm convinced that Veterinary Education is the key, but I'm not sure yet how to turn that key. Much more thought and action needed.

Photo: view of Egmond aan Zee with lighthouse on the right, with housing and low buildings surrounding the lighthouse on three sides. On the left the sea and sky, both grayish.

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